

Spiritual Leadership and Quality of Work Life an Exploratory Study on Menoufia University Hospitals

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Abstract

The objective of the research is to identify the relationship between Spiritual Leadership (SL) and Quality of Work Life (QWL) at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt. The research community consists of all employees at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt. Due to time and cost constraints, the researcher relied on the sampling method to collect data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses.

The research has reached a number of results, the most important of which are (1) the scarcity of research that focused on the study and interpretation of the relation between the study variables (SL and QWL) in the Egyptian business environment in general and Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt in particular, (2) SL is a state expressed in a set of organizational dimensions (vision, hope/faith, altruism, meaning/meaning of work, membership, organizational commitment, and productivity, which can be used to improve the QWL, (3) SL is an important tool used by successful managers in developing all employees and spreading social awareness among them in such a way as to enable them to deal with the work environment by providing job security, freedom, and independence of employees, and positive interaction between employees and good relations among themselves, (4) there is a statistically significant relationship between SL and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

The study referred to a number of recommendations, the most important of which are (1) the need for managers attention to the future vision of the hospitals, (2) the need for managers to have the element of hope and faith in the vision of the hospitals, (3) the need to have the love of altruism among the leaders in the hospitals, (4) the need for all employees of the organization to be convinced that their jobs are important and meaningful both for themselves and for others, (5) the need to deepen the membership of the organization in all its employees, (6) the need for managers to raise the level of organizational commitment (7) the need for managers to increase productivity and continuous improvement in the hospitals, (8) restructuring of the system of wages in the hospital, (9) increasing rewards in the hospital (10) the need to pay attention to the application of the principle of reward and punishment in the hospital, (11) the need to improve the wages of all employees in the hospital, (12) providing a safe and healthy work environment for all employees in the hospitals, (13) concern for achieving the welfare of hospital staff and improving the quality of the career, (14) activation of training programs but not to specific categories, (15) involvement of hospital staff in the decision-making process, (16) activating complaints and suggestions box in the hospital, (17) abiding by the principles and rules governing the nature of work in the hospital, (18) development and utilization of human capacities in the hospital, (19) the importance of achieving social integration in the hospital, (20) emphasizing the absence of a negative impact on the life of the work on the total life area of the personnel working in the hospital

1. Introduction

There are new concepts in the contemporary administrative business environment, the most important being SL (Fry, 2003; Chen & Yang, 2012).

SL is highly popular in education, health care, psychology, as well as in management research. There has been an increase in the number of studies carried out, which shows the interest in SL (Kluas & Fernando, 2016).

A number of researchers in social research, in general, and administrative research, in particular, have been interested in SL (Giacalone & Jurkiewicz, 2003).

SL plays an important role in improving the level of organizational commitment, on the one hand, and productivity on the other. This is in addition to their positive impact on the individual, the teams, the building of organizational values, and sense of community (Jerry, 2009; Chen et al., 2013).

SL belongs to the Transformational Leadership School, which focuses on behavior, messages about vision, ambition, emotional feelings, ideological and moral values, attention to individuals, and intellectual motivation of the leader and subordinates (Chen & Li, 2013).

SL plays an important role in creating a positive working environment, new working relationships, and motivating subordinates in a manner that contributes to the organization's goals efficiently and effectively (Polat, 2011).

Quality of Work Life (QWL) is not a new issue in the organization, and most studies have confirmed that quality of life is the most important theme that the organization must take into account (Narehan et al., 2014).

The issue of quality of life was first introduced in 1972 at the International Labor Relations Conference, and this theme was given more attention when General Motor launched several quality programs to improve and reform work (Gayathiri & Ramakrishnan, 2013).

QWL plays an important role for workers in all organizations of all types and sizes. Life in the workplace is as important as personal life, and the element of satisfaction is very important in both of them (Sharma & Verma, 2013).

The quality of career and other concepts has become a key determinant of the success and stability of organizations of all types and sizes (Koonmee et al., 2010).

QWL is an important part of improving and enhancing the performance of organizations of all types and sizes. The quality of life of health care organizations creates positive results for health providers and recipients (Burtson & Stichler, 2010).

The current study seeks to determine the relationship between SL and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

2. Spiritual Leadership

2.1. Spiritual Leadership Concept

SL is the use of the leader of his spiritual side as one of the motivational behaviors of his subordinates, in a way that helps them discover the moral strength that binds them to others (Lean, 2012).

SL is one of the types of leadership that seeks to satisfy the needs and desires of the employees in the organization by providing psychological needs that help them to continue working in the organization and communicate with others, and belonging to the organization in a way that leads to efficiency in the performance of business, (Chun et al., 2012).

SL is one of the methods that can be followed to improve organizational performance through leaders' attitudes that motivate employees to achieve the goals and vision of their organization (Chen & Yang, 2012).

SL is one of the forms of leadership that can be followed by leaders in an organization in a way that achieves its goals efficiently and effectively (Karadag, 2009).

SL is a set of human values that constitute the working environment of an organization, where its employees demonstrate their abilities and skills (Burkhart, 2008).

SL is a set of aspects relating to the personality of the individual, which serves as the primary engine of the physical body (Wilson et al., 2008).

SL is a set of positive emotions such as gratitude, forgiveness, and hope that have proven to help individuals engage in behaviors that contribute to productivity and the development of relationships within the organization (Bono & Mc Cullough, 2006).

SL is a form of leadership and seeks to transform the workplace into a more comfortable and productive place, on the one hand, and providing the needs of employers and workers on the other (Thanakappan, 2005).

SL is a set of values, attitudes, and behaviors necessary to motivate one's self, on the one hand, and to motivate others on the other (Fry, 2003). SL is a reliable leadership technique in motivating subordinates to achieve high levels of organizational and productive commitment. It is a set of values, attitudes, and behaviors that stimulate one's self and others in order to have a sense of survival in the spiritual life (Fry et al., 2005).

SL is a phenomenon that occurs in the organization when the leader is honest and modest in his actions and behavior in the organization in a way that reflects his respect for himself and others. It is one of

the forms of leadership that can be used to provide the basic needs of workers, on the one hand, and to achieve satisfaction on the other. This is in addition to changing the business philosophy towards the organization from being mutually beneficial with the organization that they are working to achieve their own values (Reave, 2005).

SL is one of the methods of integrating the values, processes, and systems of the organization with the values and aspirations of its personnel, in other words creating an atmosphere of harmony between individuals and the organization (Benefiel, 2005).

SL is to teach subordinates the methods that enable them to govern themselves and create the right conditions so subordinates can work freely with their leaders within the organization (Fairholm, 1996).

2.2. Spiritual Leadership Dimensions

There are six dimensions of SL (Zavvareh et al., 2013; Polat, 2011). They can be explained as follows:

1. Vision

There must be a clear vision of what the organization would like to be in the future. The term vision was rarely used in leadership literature until the 1980s. At the moment, leaders in business organizations have had to give greater attention to future direction due to the intensity of competition and technological development. Spiritual leaders try to motivate subordinates through a clear vision of the organization.

2. Hope / Faith

Hope is the desire to expect achievement; faith is beyond hope or expectation of something desirable, faith is more than just a wish for something. It depends on values, attitudes, and behaviors that ensure certainty and absolute certainty that what is desired and expected will be achieved. In general, hope and faith are the sources of belief and conviction that the vision and mission of the Organization will be realized.

3. Altruistic Love

Altruism love is the sense of integration, harmony, and well-being resulting from the care, attention, and appreciation of both self and others. This concept, also, includes the values of patience, compassion, tolerance, humility, altruism, trust, loyalty, and sincerity. In addition, the love of altruism in the SL helps to get rid of destructive feelings such as fear, anger, feeling of failure and others.

4. The meaning/significance of work

The concept of meaning refers to whether members of the organization believe that the functions they perform are significant and meaningful, and by engaging in work, individuals derive meaning and purpose from life. In addition, individuals who have an internal motivation and drive to learn are finding work, as well as individuals who want to be members of the workgroup, feel they have value and contribution to performance. It is, therefore, clear that meaning and sense of importance are associated with spirituality in the workplace.

5. Membership

Most individuals tend to work in a group or team, and they prefer to work in an environment in which leaders appreciate their contributions to achieving their goals. Leaders must, therefore, be able to create a culture that involves leaders and subordinates interested and responsible for themselves and others. This culture must create a sense of membership. SL must, therefore, take care of the workers in such a way as to create an atmosphere of friendliness and trust among all staff of the organization.

6. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is one of the main axes of organizational success. SL plays an important role in influencing the level of organizational commitment. The appropriate leadership styles lead to an increased level of job satisfaction for employees. SL also plays an important role in achieving organizational

identification and organizational loyalty through organizational commitment and the desire to remain and work in the organization.

7. Productivity

The availability of the element of hope/faith in the vision of the organization, their sense of importance and membership makes them do their best to carry out activities that achieve the vision of the organization and thereby increase productivity. It should be noted that SL plays an important role in increasing the level of job satisfaction, which in turn leads to increased productivity in the organization.

3. Quality of Work Life

3.1. Quality of Work Life Concept

QWL can be defined by two perspectives, the first from the personal point of view, namely, the perception of workers from the same place of work, and the second from the objective point of view, a set of programs and activities related to the work of the organization such as salaries, health care, decision, and occupational safety (Nekouei et al., 2014).

QWL is the right working environment that promotes and develops employee satisfaction through rewards, job security, as well as opportunities for advancement (Gayathiri & Ramakrishnan, 2013).

QWL is the degree of excellence and conditions of work that determine the nature of the relationship between the worker and the environment in which he works, in addition to the human dimension, which contributes to the overall achievement of job satisfaction of employees, thus improving the ability of individuals to perform work, and thus the performance of the organization as a whole (Shani, 2013).

QWL is a program that combines a set of principles that seek to satisfy the employees of the organization, as well as increase their desire to learn and to cope with changes that occur in environment conditions (Mirkamali & Thane, 2011).

QWL is a set of programs, methods, and theories that provide an appropriate work environment in a way that helps employees perform the tasks assigned to them, in addition to the need to give employees the authority and responsibility that suits their business (Gupta & Sharma, 2011).

QWL is a philosophy based on the fact that the employees of the organization are the most important resources, and therefore must be treated with respect and appreciation (Reddy & Redd, 2010).

QWL is an entry that contains a range of issues such as rewards, and the nature of the time spent by the worker in the work environment (Pizam, 2010).

QWL is all the organization's activities to improve the workplace, which has an impact on the productivity of the organization's employees (Lewis et al., 2001).

QWL is the satisfaction of employees with their needs and desires within the organization in which they work. In other words, that the quality of the career is the conditions and environment suitable for the workplace in a way that satisfies the employees of the organization by providing rewards and job security as well as promotion opportunities in their field (Sirgy et al., 2001).

3.2. Quality of Work Life Dimensions

The dimensions of quality of life are wage justice, working conditions of the organization, opportunities for promotion, adherence to the principles of the organization, training and development of staff, social integration, work life and social responsibility (Timossi et al., 2008; Parvar et al., 2013):

1. Wage justice

The remuneration that the individual receives from the organization must be commensurate with its needs on the one hand, and its effort on the other hand. There must be fixed ways to determine the level of remuneration that an individual receives since many workers feel that what they receive is not commensurate with the effort they are doing.

2. Working conditions of the Organization

The organization must provide safe and healthy working conditions for all its personnel so as not to be exposed to working conditions that may affect their mental or physical health. Trade unions played an important role in this area through government legislation, which in turn improved the working conditions of the Organization.

3. Promotion opportunities

Promotion opportunities play an important role in the lives of people working in the organization, and there must be real opportunities for growth and promotion on an ongoing basis, which improves the quality of the organization's career.

4. Commitment to the principles of the Organization

Individuals working in the organization must adhere to the principles and rules for their work. On the other hand, there must be an obligation on the part of the organization to take into account the fairness in the distribution of the rewards for the employees.

5. Training and Development Opportunities

The training and development of workers play an important role in improving and increasing the knowledge related to work, which is reflected positively in increasing the degree of job satisfaction and thus improve the quality of the career in addition to increasing the growth of knowledge of the staff helping them solve the problems at work.

6. Social integration

The characteristics of the work environment in the organization have a great impact on the individuals working on the one hand, as well as their respect for these characteristics, on the other hand, the most important of which is the sense of belonging to the organization, the existence of real opportunities for promotion, the non-discrimination among the individuals working in the organization.

7. Work life and total life

There is a relationship between private life and working life in the organization. Given the surrounding environmental conditions, where competition is increasing, it is difficult to separate private life from the work life of the organization. It should be noted that most employees have a strong desire to balance their personal and recreational lives and their practical lives.

8. Social responsibility

The goal of the organization is not only to make a profit, but also to take responsibility for society. Managers in all organizations must take into account the social responsibility of the organization, which requires the creation of an appropriate strategic plan that will help the organization survive. An organization that operates in a socially irresponsible manner has a short life and, therefore, does not have the status of success and stability

4. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable of SL. There is one dependent variable of QWL. From the above discussion, the research model is as shown in the following table:

Figure (1)
Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that SL have an impact on QWL. SL as measured consisted of vision, hope/faith, altruism love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity (Fry & Matherly, 2006). QWL is measured in terms of adequate compensation, working condition, the opportunity for growth, constitutionalism, the opportunity for developing, social integration, working life, and social responsibility (Timossi et al., 2008).

5. Research Questions

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature reviews that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between SL and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

In light of the review of previous studies towards SL, literature has shown that there is a significant relationship between SL and organizational commitment, productivity, and satisfaction (Fry et al., 2017). SL positively influences the spirituality of the work environment (Afsar et al., 2016). There is a statistically significant relationship between SL and OCB (Kaya, 2015). There is a significant relationship between SL and organizational learning (Shafighi et al., 2013). There is a relationship between SL and job satisfaction (Masouleh et al., 2013). In addition, SL leads to increased behavior of OCB (Chen & Yang, 2012).

As for the QWL, the literature indicated that the QWL plays the mediating role between psychological capital and the intentions of leaving the organization (Kim et al., 2017). There is a significant correlation between QWL and organizational performance (Nayak & Sahoo, 2015). There is a relationship between QWL and career path (Bahrami et al., 2013). There is a significant relationship between QWL and organizational commitment (Farjal & Varnous, 2013). There is a positive relationship between QWL and social responsibility (Tongo, 2013). In addition, there is a significant relationship between QWL and job satisfaction (Tabassum, 2012).

The second source for the research problem is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees in order to identify the relationship between SL and QWL. The researcher found, through the pilot study, several indicators; notably the important and vital role that could be played by SL in

improving QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt. As a result of the discussions given above, the research questions of this study are as follows:

- Q1: What is the relationship between SL (vision) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt?.
- Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between (Hope/Faith) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt?
- Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt?
- Q4: What are the nature and the extent of the relationship between SL (Meaning/Calling) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt?
- Q5: What is the relationship between SL (Membership) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt?
- Q6: What is the nature of the relationship between (Organizational commitment) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt?
- Q7: What is the extent of the relationship between SL (Productivity) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt?

6. Research Hypotheses

In the light of a review of previous studies towards SL, literature has shown that SL plays an important role in influencing the spirituality of the work environment (Sani et al., 2016). There is a relationship between SL and organizational performance. SL has a positive impact on organizational performance (Salehzadeh et al., 2015). There is a significant correlation between SL and QWL (Bardmili et al., 2013). There is a positive correlation between SL and the happiness of working individuals (Zavareh et al., 2013). There is a relationship between SL and employee empowerment (Esfahani et al., 2013). There is a positive relationship between SL and organizational outcomes such as organizational commitment and productivity (Fry et al., 2017). There is a relationship between SL and organizational culture. Attendance as one of the dimensions of SL plays an important role in influencing performance, which has an impact on organizational culture (Karadag, 2009).

As for the QWL, the literature indicated that there is a direct relationship between the QWL and OCB. There is an indirect relationship between emotional intelligence and OCB. QWL plays the mediating role between emotional intelligence and OCB (Alfonso et al., 2016). There is a relationship between QWL organizational commitment (Farid et al., 2015). There is a relationship between independent variables (QWL and job satisfaction) and the dependent variable (OCB) (Kasraie et al., 2014). There is a significant correlation between SL and QWL (Bahrdmili et al., 2013). There is a positive relationship between QWL and organizational commitment (Parvar et al., 2013). There is a positive relationship QWL and job engagement (Kanten & Sadullah, 2012).

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between SL and QWL.

- H1: There is no relationship between SL (vision) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt
- H2: SL (Hope/Faith) has no significant effect on QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.
- H3: There is no relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt
- H4: SL (Meaning/Calling) has no significant impact on QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.
- H5: There is no relationship between SL (Membership) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt
- H6: SL (Organizational commitment) has no significant influence on QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.
- H7: There is no relationship between SL (Productivity) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt

7. Research Strategy

7.1. Population and Sample

The study subjects are employees at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt. The total population is 3307 employees. Determination of sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

The number of samples obtained by 382 employees at Menoufia University Hospitals is presented in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Job Category	Number	Percentage	Size of Sample
Physicians	488	15%	344X 15% = 52
Nurses	2141	65%	344 X 65% = 224
Administrative Staff	678	20%	344 X 20% = 68
Total	3307	100%	344 X 100% = 344

Source: Personnel Department at Menoufia University, 2017

Proportionality with the number of employees in the research population is proved in Table (1). By using the lists of employees at the Staff Affairs Department, Menoufia University hospitals random choice of categories was attained. Table (2) illustrates the features of sample units.

Table (2) Characteristics of Items of the Sample

Demographic Variables	Number	Percentage	
1- Job Title	Physicians	125	42%
	Nurses	145	48%
	Administrative Staff	30	10%
	Total	300	100%
2- Sex	Male	120	40%
	Female	180	60%
	Total	315	100%
3- Marital Status	Single	100	33%
	Married	200	67%
	Total	300	100%
4- Age	Under 30	100	33%
	From 30 to 45	120	40%
	Above 45	80	27%
	Total	300	100%
5- Educational Level	University	170	57.6%
	Post Graduate	130	43%
	Total	300	100%
6- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	100	33%
	From 5 to 10	130	43%
	More than 10	70	24%
	Total	300	100%

7.2. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the relationship between SL and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt. A survey research method was used to collect data. The questionnaire included three questions, relating to SL, QWL, and biographical information of employees at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt. About 382 survey questionnaires were distributed. Multiple follow-ups yielded 300 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 78%.

7.3. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 35-item scale SL section is based on Fry & Matherly, 2006. There were five items measuring vision, five items measuring hope/faith, seven items measuring altruism love, four items measuring the meaning/significance of work, five items measuring membership, four items measuring commitment, and five items measuring productivity at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

The 33-item scale QWL section is based on Timossi et al., 2008. There were three items measuring adequate compensation, six items measuring working condition, three items measuring opportunity for growth, four items measuring constitutionalism, five items measuring opportunity for developing, four items measuring social integration, three items measuring working life, and five items measuring social responsibility. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

7.4. Methods of Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach’s Alpha, (2) Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and (3) the statistical testing of hypotheses which includes F- test and T-test. They are found in SPSS.

8. Hypotheses Testing

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics were performed to find out means and standard deviations of SL and QWL.

Table (3) shows the mean and standard deviations of SL and QWL

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
SL	Vision	3.88	0.797
	Hope/Faith	4.09	0.710
	Altruistic Love	3.77	0.793
	Meaning/Calling	4.11	0.767
	Membership	4.15	0.777
	Organizational Commitment	3.95	0.725
	Productivity	4.18	0.723
	Total Measurement	4.01	0.654
QWL	Adequate Compensation	3.95	0.730
	Working Condition	3.81	0.825
	Opportunity for Growth	4.04	0.878
	Constitutionalism	4.10	0.780
	Opportunity for Developing	4.14	0.789
	Social Integration	3.93	0.754
	Working Life	3.99	0.910
	Social Responsibility	4.18	0.727
	Total Measurement	4.01	0.701

According to Table (4), the first issue examined was the different facets of SL (vision, hope/faith, altruism love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, commitment, and productivity). According to Table (4), among the various facets of SL, most of the respondents identified the presence of vision ($M=3.88$, $SD=0.797$), hope/faith ($M=4.09$, $SD=0.710$), altruism love ($M=3.77$, $SD=0.793$), meaning/significance of work ($M=4.11$, $SD=0.797$), membership ($M=4.15$, $SD=0.777$), organizational commitment ($M=3.95$, $SD=0.725$), and productivity ($M=4.18$, $SD=0.723$).

The second issue examined was the different facets of QWL (adequate compensation, working condition, the opportunity for growth, constitutionalism, the opportunity for developing, social integration, working life, and social responsibility). Most of the respondents identified the presence of adequate compensation ($M=3.95$, $SD=0.730$), working condition ($M=3.81$, $SD=0.825$), opportunity for growth ($M=4.04$, $SD=0.878$), constitutionalism ($M=4.10$, $SD=0.780$), opportunity for developing ($M = 4.14$, $SD=0.789$), social integration ($M=3.93$, $SD=0.754$), working life ($M=3.99$, $SD=0.910$), and social responsibility ($M=4.18$, $SD=0.727$).

8.1. Evaluating Reliability

Data analysis was conducted. All scales were first subjected to reliability analysis. Cronbach’s Alpha was used to assess the reliability of the scales. Item analysis indicated that dropping any item from the scales would not significantly raise the alphas.

Table (4) Reliability of SL and QWL

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
SL	Vision	5	0.899
	Hope/Faith	5	0.815
	Altruistic Love	7	0.821
	Meaning/Calling	4	0.770
	Membership	5	0.839
	Organizational Commitment	4	0.808
	Productivity	5	0.862
	Total Measurement	35	0.908
QWL	Adequate Compensation	3	0.776
	Working Condition	6	0.834
	Opportunity for Growth	3	0.773
	Constitutionalism	4	0.772
	Opportunity for Developing	5	0.832
	Social Integration	4	0.799
	Working Life	3	0.744
	Social Responsibility	5	0.852
	Total Measurement	33	0.966

To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach’s Alpha test was conducted. Table (4) shows the reliability results for SL, QWL, and OCB. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were therefore excellent, according to Langdridge’s (2004) criteria.

Table (4) presents the reliability of SL. The reliabilities of s vision, hope/faith, altruism love, the meaning/significance of work, membership, organizational commitment, and productivity are generally higher. The 35 items of SL are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.908. The vision, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.899. The 5 items related to hope/faith, are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.815 while the 7 items of altruism love are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.821. The meaning/significance of work which consists of 4 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.770. The 5 items related to membership are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.839 while the 4 items of organizational commitment are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.808. Productivity which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.862. Thus, the internal consistency of SL can be acceptable.

According to Table (4), the 33 items of QWL are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.966. The adequate compensation, which consists of 3 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.776. The 6 items related to the working condition, are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.834 while the 3 items of opportunity for growth are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.773. The constitutionalism which consists of 4 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.772. The 5 items related to opportunity for developing are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.832 while the 4 items of social integration are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.799 while the 3 items of working life are reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.744. Social responsibility which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the Cronbach’s Alpha is 0.852. Thus, the internal consistency of QWL can be acceptable.

Accordingly, two scales were defined, SL (35 variables), where Cronbach’s Alpha represented about 0.908, and QWL (33 variables), where Cronbach’s Alpha represented about 0.966.

8.2. The Means, St. Deviations and Correlation among Variables

Table (5) Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	SL	QWL
Spiritual Leadership	4.01	0.654	1	
Quality of Work Life	4.01	0.701	0.979**	1

Table (5) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of significant correlation between variables (SL, and QWL). The level of SL of employees is high

(Mean=4.01; SD=0.654), while QWL is (Mean=4.01; SD=0.701). The overall correlation between SL and QWL is 0.979.

8.3. The Correlation between SL and QWL

The relationship between SL and BB at the industrial companies in Sadat city in Egypt is presented in the following table:

Table (6) Correlation Matrix between SL and QWL

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Vision	1							
Hope/Faith	0.677**	1						
Altruistic Love	0.505**	0.660**	1					
Meaning/Calling	0.399**	0.832**	0.807**	1				
Membership	0.388**	0.843**	0.766**	0.973**	1			
Commitment	0.922**	0.764**	0.588**	0.530**	0.514**	1		
Productivity	0.632**	0.886**	0.702**	0.880**	0.872**	0.761**	1	
QWL	0.617**	0.903**	0.868**	0.955**	0.941**	0.727**	0.925**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

Based on the Table (6), the correlation between SL (vision) and QWL is 0.617. For SL (hope/faith) and QWL, the value is 0.903 whereas SL (altruistic love) and QWL show correlation value of 0.868. Also, the correlation between SL (meaning/calling) and QWL is 0.955. For SL (membership) and QWL, the value is 0.941 whereas SL (organizational commitment) and QWL show correlation value of 0.727. Finally, the correlation between SL (productivity) and QWL is 0.925. The overall correlation between SL and QWL is 0.979.

8.4. Spiritual Leadership (Vision) and QWL

The relationship between SL (Vision) and QWL is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between SL (vision) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt

As Table (7) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.700 demonstrating that the 3 independent variables of SL (Vision) construe QWL significantly.

Furthermore, the value of R square, 3 independent variables of SL (Vision) can explain 49% of the total factors in QWL level. Hence, 51% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (7) MRA Results for SL (Vision) and QWL

The Variables of Vision	Beta	R	R ²
1. I understand and am committed to my organization's vision.	0.510**	0.654	0.427
2. My workgroup has a vision statement that brings out the best in me.	0.003	0.492	0.242
3. My organization's vision inspires my best performance.	0.116	0.487	0.237
4. I have faith in my organization's vision for its employees.	0.227*	0.512	0.262
5. My organization's vision is clear and compelling to me.	0.039	0.465	0.216
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.700 0.490 56.481 5, 294 3.01 0.000	
** P < .01	* P < .05		

8.5. Spiritual Leadership (Hope/Faith) and QWL

The relationship between SL (Hope/Faith) and QWL is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: SL (Hope/Faith) has no significant effect on QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

Table (8) MRA Results for SL (Hope/Faith) and QWL

The Variables of Hope/Faith	Beta	R	R ²
1. I have faith in my organization, and I am willing to “do whatever it takes” to insure that it accomplishes its mission.	0.465**	0.776	0.602
2. I persevere and exert extra effort to help my organization succeed because I have faith in what it stands for.	0.040	0.740	0.547
3. I always do my best in my work because I have faith in my organization and its leaders.	0.089	0.545	0.297
4. I set challenging goals for my work because I have faith in my organization and want us to succeed.	0.419**	0.800	0.640
5. I demonstrate my faith in my organization and its mission by doing everything I can to help us succeed.	0.158**	0.490	0.240
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.923 0.852 338.203 5, 294 3.01 0.000	
** P < .01			

As Table (8) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.923. This means that QWL has been significantly explained by the 5 independent variables of SL (Hope/Faith). As a result of the value of R², the five independent variables of SL (Hope/Faith) justified only 85% of the total factors in QWL level. Hence, 15% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.6. Spiritual Leadership (Altruistic Love) and QWL

The relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and QWL is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between SL (Altruistic Love) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt

Table (9) MRA Results for SL (Altruistic Love) and QWL

The Variables of Altruistic Love	Beta	R	R ²
1. My organization really cares about its people.	0.228	0.767	0.588
2. My organization is kind and considerate toward its workers, and when they are suffering, wants to do something about it.	0.316	0.768	0.589
3. The leaders in my organization “walk the walk” as well as “talk the talk.”	0.747	0.773	0.597
4. My organization is trustworthy and loyal to its employees.	0.163**	0.508	0.258
5. My organization does not punish honest mistakes.	0.279**	0.527	0.277
6. The leaders in my organization are honest and without false pride.	0.189**	0.427	0.182
7. The leaders in my organization have the courage to stand up for their people.	0.067	0.376	0.141
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.892 0.795 161.684 7, 292 2.63 0.000	
** P < .01			

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.892 demonstrating that the 5 independent variables of SL (Altruistic Love) construe QWL significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 5 independent variables of SL (Altruistic Love) can explain only 79% of the total factors in QWL level.

Hence, 21% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.7. Spiritual Leadership (Meaning/Calling) and QWL

The relationship between SL (Meaning/Calling) and QWL is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

H4: SL (Meaning/Calling) has no significant impact on QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

Table (10) MRA Results for SL (Meaning/Calling) and QWL

The Variables of Meaning/Calling	Beta	R	R ²
1. The work I do is very important to me.	0.202**	0.666	0.443
2. My job activities are personally meaningful to me.	0.342**	0.723	0.522
3. The work I do is meaningful to me.	0.280**	0.786	0.617
4. The work I do makes a difference in people’s lives.	0.390**	0.819	0.670
▪ MCC		0.960	
▪ DC		0.920	
▪ Calculated F		862.508	
▪ Degree of Freedom		4, 295	
▪ Indexed F		3.31	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
** P < .01			

As Table (10) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.960. This means that QWL has been significantly explained by the 6 independent variables of SL (Meaning/Calling). As a result of the value of R² the six independent variables of SL (Meaning/Calling) justified 92% of the total factors in QWL level. Hence, 8% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.8. Spiritual Leadership (Membership) and QWL

The relationship between SL (Membership) and QWL is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

H5: There is no relationship between SL (Membership) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt

Table (11) MRA Results for SL (Membership) and QWL

The Variables of Vision	Beta	R	R ²
1. I feel my organization understands my concerns.	0.018	0.678	0.459
2. I feel my organization appreciates me, and my work.	0.378**	0.819	0.670
3. I feel highly regarded by my leadership.	0.364**	0.773	0.597
4. I feel I am valued as a person in my job.	0.248**	0.786	0.617
5. I feel my organization demonstrates respect for me and my work.	0.192**	0.651	0.423
▪ MCC		0.960	
▪ DC		0.922	
▪ Calculated F		696.679	
▪ Degree of Freedom		5, 294	
▪ Indexed F		3.01	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
** P < .01			

Table (11) proves that there is a relationship between SL (Membership) and QWL in a significance level of 0,000. Moreover, the value of R², the 6 independent variables of SL (Membership) can explain 92% of the total differentiation in QWL level. For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of SL (Membership) and QWL is obtained. Because MCC is 0.960, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.9. Spiritual Leadership (Organizational Commitment) and QWL

The relationship between SL (Organizational Commitment) and QWL is determined. The six hypothesis to be tested is:

H6: SL (Organizational commitment) has no significant influence on OP at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

Table (12) MRA Results for SL (Organizational Commitment) and QWL

The Variables of Organizational Commitment	Beta	R	R ²
1. I do not feel like “part of the family” in this organization.	0.625**	0.769	0.591
2. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.	0.159**	0.527	0.277
3. I talk up this organization to my friends as a great place to work for.	0.073	0.563	0.316
4. I really feel as if my organization’s problems are my own.	0.110*	0.488	0.238
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.812 0.659 142.472 4, 295 3.31 0.000	
** P < .01		* P < .05	

As Table (12) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.812. This means that QWL has been significantly explained by the 5 variables of SL (Organizational Commitment). As a result of the value of R² the six independent variables of SL (Organizational Commitment) justified 65% of the total factors in QWL level. Hence, 35% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

8.10. Spiritual Leadership (Productivity) and QWL

The relationship between SL (Productivity) and QWL is determined. The seven hypothesis to be tested is:

H7: There is no relationship between SL (Productivity) and QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt

Table (13) proves that there is a relationship between SL (Productivity) and QWL. As a result of the value of R², the 5 independent variables of SL (Productivity) can explain 87% of the total differentiation in QWL level. For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of SL (Productivity) and QWL is obtained. Because MCC is 0.936, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (13) MRA Results for SL (Productivity) and QWL

The Variables of Vision	Beta	R	R ²
1. Everyone is busy in my department/grade; there is little idle time.	0.284**	0.778	0.605
2. In my department, work quality is a high priority for all workers.	0.107**	0.774	0.599
3. In my department, everyone gives his/her best efforts.	0.196**	0.770	0.592
4. My work group is very productive.	0.402**	0.789	0.622
5. My work group is very efficient in getting maximum, the output from the resources (money, people, equipment, etc.) we have available	0.169**	0.637	0.405
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.936 0.877 417.391 5, 294 3.01 0.000	
** P < .01			

9. The Research Results

By reviewing the results of the descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the hypotheses of the research, the study reached a set of results as follows:

1. The scarcity of research that focused on the study and interpretation of the relation between the study variables (SL and QWL) in the Egyptian business environment in general and Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt in particular.
2. SL is a statement expressed in a set of organizational dimensions: vision, hope/faith, altruism, the meaning/meaning of work, membership, organizational commitment, and productivity, which can be used to improve the QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.
3. SL is an important tool used by successful managers in developing all employees and spreading social awareness among them in such a way as to enable them to deal with the work environment by providing job security, freedom, and independence of employees, and positive interaction between employees and good relations among themselves.
4. The general average of SL at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt is fairly high. The vision as one of the dimensions of SL ranked first, followed by the concerned or the second, the hope and faith in the third place, the membership in the fourth place, the organizational commitment in the fifth place, the altruism love ranked sixth, and finally the productivity as one of the dimensions of SL at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt.
5. The general average of the behavior of development at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt is somewhat low. Behavior was followed by verbal, physical development, followed by physical development in second place, physical development versus property in third place, and social BB in fourth place as a dimension of BB at the industrial companies at Sadat city in Egypt.
6. There is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of SL and the dimensions of QWL at Menoufia University Hospitals in Egypt.

10. Recommendations

In light of the previous results, the researcher concludes with a set of recommendations. The most important of these recommendations can be summarized as follows:

1. The need for managers attention to the future vision of their units and departments, and must be characterized by realistic vision and the possibility of implementation with the highest degree of efficiency and effectiveness, and can be done through the involvement of staff in their development, which entails the effort and strives to achieve.
2. The need for managers to have the element of hope and faith in the vision of the Organization, since they are the source of belief and conviction that the vision and mission of the Organization will be achieved, and can be done through rewarding material rewards on the one hand and involvement in their development on the other.
3. The need to have the love of altruism among the leaders in the organization, or in other words the need to have a sense of integration and attention and appreciation for both self and others, and can be done by teaching managers the values of patience, honesty and honesty, as this will lead to a sense of workers Which is the love of altruism. In addition, the love of altruism among managers will help to eliminate destructive feelings such as fear, anger, feelings of failure, and false pride.
4. The need for all employees of the organization to be convinced that their jobs are important and meaningful both for themselves and for others. Work has social meaning and adds value to them, and work helps them to serve others and thus derive a purpose and meaning in life.
5. The need to deepen the membership of the organization in all its employees, since the sense of employees belonging to a particular organization creates an atmosphere of friendliness and trust between the employees and some of them, and workers and their leaders on the other hand, which creates the sense of membership and recognition.
6. The need for managers to raise the level of organizational commitment, as appropriate leadership methods lead to increased job satisfaction among employees, which in turn raises the level of organizational commitment to them. In addition, the sense of belonging to the organization will create a

sense of loyalty to the organization and would like to remain in it, since the culture of the organization is based on altruism, which raises the level of organizational commitment.

7. The need for managers to increase productivity and continuous improvement, as the availability of hope and faith in the vision of the organization, their sense of importance, and membership will do their utmost to achieve the vision and mission of the organization, and work on improvement and continuous development, which leads to increased productivity. In addition, following the method of SL will contribute mainly to increase the productivity of the organization. In other words, it is necessary to take care of spirituality in the workplace through SL, which leads to a sense of the quality of work environment, thus increasing the level of job satisfaction, organizational commitment and thus increasing productivity.
8. Re-studying and structuring of the system of wages in the hospital in a way that allows them to get the appropriate return for their efforts. This can be achieved through the following:
 - Increasing rewards in the hospital in order to meet the low wages and be commensurate with the individual effort in the hospital. This can be achieved by increasing the resources of the hospital from the diversity and multiplicity of services provided to members of the community, in providing the service.
 - The need to pay attention to the application of the principle of reward and punishment in the hospital in terms of the item of wages and bonuses, as a group of workers receives financial rewards much higher than the effort and vice versa. Some workers receive financial rewards far less than the effort in the hospital.
 - The need to improve the wages of all employees in the hospital. This can be done by multiplicity and diversity of services provided by the hospital to the members of the community in a way that increases the self resources or by addressing the concerned parties to raise wages.
9. Providing a safe and healthy work environment for all employees in different educational hospitals. This can be achieved through the following:
 - The need for hospital officials to take care of the physical conditions of the work in terms of lighting, ventilation, and cleanliness.
 - The need to provide safety means and different protection methods for the hospital staff or patients.
10. Concern for achieving the welfare of hospital staff and improving the quality of the career in terms of providing promotion opportunities and being objective in accordance with specific standards and controls. There should be participation by decision makers, safety and occupational health, and an increased sense of safety and job stability among the hospital staff.
11. Activation of training programs but not to specific categories. Training includes all aspects of technical, humanitarian and moral; the training periods are continuing, as training plays an important role in raising morale and satisfaction of employees. This increases the staff opportunities for promotion and reveals their abilities and skills.
12. Involvement of hospital staff in the decision-making process, in view of the nature and sensitivity of work in the hospital, which concerns the lives of citizens. That needs a large area of freedom to make decisions; workers feel they are making plans and programs themselves for themselves, in organizational symmetry.
13. Activating complaints and suggestions box in the hospital in a way that helps workers to express their opinions and suggestions, which leads to improving the quality of service provided by the hospital.
14. Abiding by the principles and rules governing the nature of work in the hospital for all individuals, but not favor and courtesy of some individuals at the expense of others.
15. Development and utilization of human capacities in the hospital. This can be done by increasing the knowledge of its employees by encouraging them to attend training courses or by completing their higher studies, which leads to multiple sources of knowledge.
16. The importance of achieving social integration in the hospital through the need to respect and appreciate the ideas and opinions of all staff in the hospital, to spread the spirit of cooperation and mutual respect among all personnel working in the hospital of different job categories.
17. Emphasizing the absence of a negative impact on the life of the work on the total life area of the personnel working in the hospital. This can be done by attention to the schedule of rest so as not to affect

the quality of service provided adversely, and that there is no increase in the volume of tasks and work entrusted to an individual in the hospital in a way that negatively affects his personal life.

18. Emphasizing the social responsibility of the hospital by improving the mental image of the hospital members of the community, to develop and improve the quality of service provided by the hospital to members of the community, in addition to the need to pay attention to the good treatment of all personnel working in the hospital. Its impact is reflected on the treatment of patients and the public and thus on the quality of service provided by the hospital.
19. The officials in the hospital should pay more attention to the staff, through the identification of their wishes and needs and trying to realize them commensurate with their objectives in order to improve the process of organizational identification.

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